

Coding scheme

Defining Security Debt: A Case Study Based On Practice

Parent code	Code	Brief description	Link to the results	# of occurrences
Context	Project description	Brief description of the current developed project	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	36
	Project size	Measured by the interviewee on a scale of small, medium, large (or LOC)	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	23
	Participant project time	Number of years that the respondent has worked on the current project	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	19
	Total project duration	Number of years since the current project started	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	31
	Team size	Total number of members in the specific team (including the business side)	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	37
	Number of developers	Number of developers in the specific team	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	25
	Hats/roles	Identify which roles the respondent has	Not related to specific results, but provided an overview of the respondents' backgrounds.	36
Technical debt (TD)	Total TD description	Descriptions of how the respondent understands TD. This code includes all the different characteristics mentioned.	RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SDE6: SD is explained to have similar characteristics as TD 	74

			RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?	
	TD description - Not deliberate TD	TD description specifically related to non deliberate TD (and TD due to technology change)	RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDE6: SD is explained to have similar characteristics as TD RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?	20
	TD description - Deliberate TD	TD description specifically related to deliberate TD	RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDE6: SD is explained to have similar characteristics as TD RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?	35
	TD description - Maintenance	TD description specifically related to additional system maintenance	RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDE6: SD is explained to have similar characteristics as TD RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?	18
	TD example	Examples of TD items to further understand how the respondent perceives TD in practice	RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDE6: SD is explained to have similar characteristics as TD RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?	34

Security debt (SD)	SD description	Descriptions of how the respondent understands SD. This code includes all the different characteristics mentioned.	<p>RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All security debt explanations (SDE): SDE1, SDE2, SDE3, ..., SDE10 <p>RQ1.1: What is the difference between security debt and security vulnerabilities?</p> <p>RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?</p> <p>RQ2: What are the accumulation patterns of security debt?</p>	68
	SD example	Examples of SD items to further understand how the respondent perceives SD in practice	<p>RQ1: What is the definition of security debt from the perspective of the practitioners?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All security debt explanations (SDE): SDE1, SDE2, SDE3, ..., SDE10 <p>RQ1.1: What is the difference between security debt and security vulnerabilities?</p> <p>RQ1.2: What is the relationship between security debt and technical debt?</p> <p>RQ2: What are the accumulation patterns of security debt?</p>	16
	SD vs security vulnerabilities	The differences and similarities between SD and security vulnerabilities	<p>RQ1.1: What is the difference between security debt and security vulnerabilities?</p> <p>RQ2: What are the accumulation patterns of security debt?</p>	41